

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF CNT REINFORCED COMPOSITES IN CRASH

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ABSTRACT

Properties of traditional fibre reinforced polymer composites (FRP) are being increasingly stretched with the modification of nano-sized materials. Modelling strategies also need to be developed continuously to be able to simulate and predict the performance of the nano-materials modified FRP. In this study, crash behaviour of an epoxy/UD-CF weave composite hat stringer structure with and without carbon nanotubes (CNT) deposited on CF reinforcement through an electrophoretic deposition (EPD) process was simulated in order to develop a constitutive model to analyse the mechanical response of the CFRP composite structure under the influence of CNT.

1 INTRODUCTION

A complete database of the mechanical properties of an epoxy polymer reinforced with unidirectional carbon fibre weave is established in [1]. Then the selected material data base, in connection to a physically based model for damage initiation and failure progression developed by [2]-[4], is used for analysis of an industrially common composite demonstrator, a hat stringer, during the current project. Then another composite system, epoxy reinforced with CNTs deposited UD CF fabric, is fully characterised to tailor the material data for the damage model. Later, structural analysis using the CNT reinforced composite material was also carried out and the results were compared against each other and the outcomes are discussed with respect to the material systems and their impact on structural performance. The design of the demonstrator follows requirements from industrial end users and makes use of the constitutive law previously implemented. Three different laminate configurations (UD, Cross ply and Quasi-isotropic) were selected for simulation. A three-point bending test, shown in Figure 1, was planned for simulation purposes. All configurations are simulated for both material systems, with and without CNT reinforcement, and the results were compared against each other to consider damage initiation and failure progression.

Figure 1: Hat stringer geometry

2 MODELLING ROUTINE

Most of the widespread material models for failure of composite materials focus on failure initiation and provide no or simplified models of the post-failure behaviour. In order to capture the correct response and energy absorption, the physics associated with failure mechanisms and damage growth of composite materials must be included in a material model. The current material model [2]-[4] represents the failure mechanisms of a transverse isotropic ply at a micromechanical level accounting for failure onset and growth. The model is based on Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) i.e. there is a damage variable accounting for the type and/or distribution of defects that characterize damage. The failure modes, fibre and matrix failure both in tension and compression, are treated individually.

Damage growth is the main dissipative mechanism in CFRP. This is modelled through a damage variable, d , and the effect of damage is accounted by allowing the relevant stress components to be degraded. Once a failure criterion reaches one, the damage variable is activated and acts on its respective failure mode by degrading the stress. The damage variables are defined from 0, at an onset strain $\varepsilon = \varepsilon^0$ representing the undamaged state, and 1 representing the fully damaged state at a final strain $\varepsilon = \varepsilon^f$. In the current implementation, d linearly degrades the stress components to zero for tensile failure and fibre compressive failure. Damage starts when one of the failures is activated. Before damage initiation the model response is linear elastic and transversely isotropic. The section of the model related to failure initiation has two purposes: (1) compute the failure index of the activated failure criterion and (2) establish the governing equations for variables that will be further used (e.g. compute the damage variable). The failure and damage criteria include:

- Fibre tensile
- Fibre compressive
- Matrix tensile
- Matrix compressive

As any other tool, this code requires appropriate and careful usage. The main points that require special attention are summarized here:

- The code was developed for the Abaqus software explicit code. The usage in other Finite Element (FE) packages requires the user to make correspondence between the nomenclature used by VUMAT variables and the nomenclature used by the other FE package.
- It is recommended to use reduced integration elements with hourglass control to stabilize the model.
- The use of regular meshes with elements with an aspect ratio of one is strongly recommended. This point will be improved in the next version.
- The introduction of the mechanical constants must follow the order stated explicitly inside the subroutine.
- Special attention to the energy of the whole model, kinetic energy, Strain Energy (SE) and Artificial Energy (AE) is required to make sure that the model is stable. The “artificial” or numerical energies should be negligible compared to “real” energies such as the strain energy and the kinetic energy.

3 COMPOSITE MANUFACTURE

An epoxy system, Araldite®LY556/Aradur®917/accelerator DY070 (Huntsman) with a mixing ratio of 100/90/0.5 (parts by weight), was used as the matrix for the composite structure. A UD weave composed of Tenax HTS45 E23 12K for warp and htm el 70 Tex verre polyamide for weft, which has a surface weight of 205 g/m² (Procher) was used as the CF reinforcement. The CF weave was deposited with industrial level multi-walled CNT through an EPD treatment and using a waterborne dispersion of CNT, Aquacyl™ AQ0302 (Nanocyl). In order to ensure a fair comparison, CF weave

that went through an EPD bath but with just deionized water without any CNTs was used in the reference composite structure. The details of the EPD treatment can be found in [5], which will not be illustrated here. Two concentrations of CNT waterborne suspension, 0.005 wt% and 0.025 wt%, were used to treat the CF weave, leading to a deposit density of 0.54 g/m² and 1.90 g/m², respectively. The CFRP hat stringers with and without CNT deposited on the CF weave were manufactured by vacuum infusion.

4 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the modelling performed in the current study each ply of the composite beam shown in Figure 1 is defined as a 3D deformable part and meshed using solid element C3D8R. The supports and the impactor are modelled as analytical rigid parts. The assembly and the applied load and boundary conditions are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Assembly of the composite beam in three-point bending case

As can be seen on the mesh, the mesh directly below the impactor is more refined compare to the mesh of the other areas as we are interested in capturing the failure in the impact zone. For computational efficiency, the composite section is divided in two and damage and failure model is applied to the section containing the refined mesh only. For through the thickness effects, each of the layers of composite have one element through their thicknesses. All the layers are tied together. Cohesive surfaces for delamination modelling are defined between layers 2-3, 4-5 and 6-7. Adding cohesive surfaces will increase the computational time. The interaction definition as general contact imposes a friction coefficient of 0.3 and shear traction of 0.1 as well. The material properties used for composite is referenced in the previous sections.

Three different laminate configurations (UD, Quasi-isotropic and Cross Ply) and also three different type of materials (reference, EPD 0.005% and EPD 0.025%) are compared. In Figures 3, the load-displacement responses are plotted. In the left column, the results are plotted for each different type of laminate configurations while in the right column results are plotted for each type of materials.

The results from the simulation of the demonstrator using the different material system, as mentioned before, are shown in Figure 4 which shows the deformed shape of the beam while presenting the damage variable for failure index on matrix compression.

The possibilities for investigation are to post process, in addition to failure indexes, damage variables for fibre and matrix in tension and compression and normal and shear stress and strains at tension and compression.

Figure 3: Load-displacement responses for the combination of laminate configurations (left) and materials (right)

Figure 3, which shows the response from force-displacement can be used to interpret the energy absorption of the cases. It is obvious, from the left column of the Figure 3, that the EPD 0.025% has always the weakest performance between the three materials, where, from the middle figure in the right column in Figure 3, it is clear that the QI laminate configuration can absorb more energy for this material than the other two configurations. This observation is also visible from the middle row in Figure 4 which shows the failure index of the matrix in compression for the EPD 0.025%. The damage is spread almost over the entire area, yet the QI laminate shows less deformation/damage spread compare to the other two configurations.

Now considering the comparison between the reference material and EPD 0.005%, it can be seen from the left column in Figure 3 that the two perform very closely and the difference is not very significant. However, Figure 4 shows slightly better performance for the EPD 0.005% material in terms of lower deformation and less matrix damage propagation in comparison to the reference material.

Figure 4: Failure index on matrix compression for the material matrix

Since the coupon tests in the lab also showed an improved performance from EPD 0.005% compare to the other two, the validation of the numerical simulation is of importance. Currently, Hat stringer samples are being manufactured in the lab for the laminate configuration Cross ply, by all the three aforementioned materials to undergo the three-point bending test. Once the testing is done the results will be plotted against the numerical analysis to validate the model.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the current contribution an epoxy/UD-CF weave composite system with and without CNT deposited on CF reinforcement through an EPD process was manufactured into a hat stringer structure via vacuum infusion. A physically based constitutive model was developed to study the failure initiation and damage progression of the laminated composite materials. Three different laminate configurations, UD, quasi isotropic and cross ply, were tested for the three-point bending loading case.

The ABAQUS software was used for simulations in combination with a VUMAT subroutine. The results of the analysis were visualized in terms of force-displacement figures and the failure index of matrix in compression. The results from the numerical simulations are verified against the coupon experiments in the lab which are published in other work during the project.

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